

A comparative study on the surface chemistry and electronic transport properties of Bi_2Te_3 synthesized through hydrothermal and thermolysis routes

Hazal Batili^{a,*}, Bejan Hamawandi^a, Adem Björn Ergül^a, Rafal Szukiewicz^b, Maciej Kuchowicz^b, Muhammet S. Toprak^{a,*}

^a Department of Applied Physics, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, SE-106 91 Stockholm, Sweden

^b Institute of Experimental Physics, University of Wrocław, Maxa Borna 9, 50-204 Wrocław, Poland

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Bismuth telluride- Bi_2Te_3 is the most promising material for harvesting thermal energy near room temperature. There are numerous works on Bi_2Te_3 reporting significantly different transport properties, with no clear connection to the synthetic routes used and the resultant surface chemistry of the synthesized materials. It is of utmost importance to characterize the constituent particles' surface and interfaces to get a better understanding of their influence on the transport properties, that will significantly improve the material design starting from the synthesis step. Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) is a promising technique, enabling the formation of thick films using colloidal suspensions of pre-made nanoparticles, which can enable the study of the effect of surface chemistry, in connection to the synthetic route, on the material's transport properties. In order to explore the differences in surface chemistry and the resultant transport properties in relation to the synthetic scheme used, here we report on Bi_2Te_3 synthesized through two wet-chemical routes in water (Hydro-) and oil (Thermo-) as the solvents. XRD analysis showed a high phase purity of the synthesized materials. SEM analysis revealed hexagonal platelet morphology of the synthesized materials, which were then used to fabricate EPD films. Characterization of the EPD films reveal significant differences between the Hydro- and Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 samples, leading to about 8 times better electrical conductivity values in the Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 . XPS analysis revealed a higher metal oxides content in the Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 sample, contributing to the formation of a resistive layer, thus

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: batili@kth.se (H. Batili), toprak@kth.se (M.S. Toprak).

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lowering the electrical conductivity. Arrhenius plots of electrical conductivity vs inverse temperature was used for the estimation of the activation energy for conduction, revealing a higher activation energy need for the Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ film, in agreement with the resistive barrier oxide content. Both the samples exhibited negative Seebeck coefficient (*S*) in the order of 160–170 mV/K. The small difference in *S* of Hydro- and Thermo-Bi₂Te₃ films was explained by the effective medium theory, revealing that the magnitude of *S* is linearly correlated with the surface oxide content. Based on the findings, TE materials synthesized through thermolysis route is recommended for further studies using soft treatment/processing of pre-made TE materials. EPD platform presented here is shown to clearly expose the differences in the electronic transport in connection to nanoparticle surface chemistry, proving a promising methodology for the evaluation of morphology, size and surface chemistry dependence of electronic transport for a wide range of materials.

1. Introduction

Our energy demand is increasing every year and any material technology that can harvest various source of energy converting into electrical energy are attracting increasing attention. The research interest starting to focus more on the greener and more sustainable energy harvesting technologies such as, thermoelectric (TE), piezoelectric, and photovoltaic [1,2]. The capability of TE materials and devices harvesting waste heat at a wide range of temperatures is distinguishing them from other methods. These materials can interconvert between heat-gradient and electricity, without needing any carrier fluid/gas, and being free from vibration-noise and maintenance, attracted a great deal of interest to TE materials and devices. The efficiency of a TE material is generally evaluated through the dimensionless figure-of-merit, *ZT*, which is defined as $(S^2\sigma T)/\kappa$, where *S* is the Seebeck coefficient, defining the voltage generated in the material by the temperature gradient, σ is the electrical conductivity, κ is the thermal conductivity, and *T* is the absolute temperature. Power factor (PF) is used for electronic transport properties and is defined as $S^2\sigma$. Ideally, good TE materials should have high PF accompanied with low κ .

Low-temperature efficient TE materials have been limited to Bi₂Te₃ alloys since their discovery, due to their promising properties for applications at ambient temperature regime, up to about 200 °C [3,4]. There are many different routes reported for the synthesis of Bi₂Te₃ nanostructures in bulk scale, including solvothermal [3,5,6], polyol [7–9], hydrothermal [10–12], thermolysis [13,14], chemical alloying [15], metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) [16], electrodeposition [17], and mechanochemical alloying [18–21]. Various morphologies of Bi₂Te₃ including nanoparticles, nanoplates, nanocrystalline films, nanorods, nanotubes, nanowires and nanoflowers have been reported (see Table S1). Microwave (MW) assisted wet-chemical synthetic routes have recently been demonstrated to be advantageous for the synthesis of Bi₂Te₃ materials in large-scale, and high reproducibility of the performance [9,10].

TE materials are generally used in the bulk form, making it possible to develop rigid TE generators modules with a limited contact area to harvest the energy. In recent years film based TEGs are desired due to availability of various grades of waste-heat in many different forms and large-areas. Therefore, scalable TE film fabrication development is becoming essential to advance the TE technology to niche areas. Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) is one of the scalable techniques that uses electrophoresis to migrate and deposit charged nanoparticles (NPs) in a suspension on the oppositely charged electrode under the influence of an electric field. The technique has been successfully used with various types of materials from polymers and proteins to ceramics and TEs [22–27]. During EPD process there are no chemical reactions taking place, allowing the preparation of films from as-made NPs without any change in size, morphology or the surface chemistry of the particles. This will enable the study of the effects of particle properties, surface chemistry, interfaces, and various additives on the electronic transport properties of the films. The details of the preparation of TE films via EPD were reported in our previous publication [27].

The correlation between the synthetic method used, and the resultant microstructure, surface chemistry and transport properties of

nanomaterials has not received the attention it deserves, causing large discrepancy between the reported results on the transport properties of a given material (see Table S1). It is, therefore, important to optimize the materials' properties for a given application through various synthesis and processing routes to understand in detail its microstructure-surface-transport property relationships. Here we present a comparative work on Bi₂Te₃ nanostructures synthesized using water and oil as the solvents with the help of MW-assisted heating. This is followed by their assembly into thick films using the EPD method, which allows for the study of interfaces of as-made materials. The materials' surface chemistry, and the resultant electronic transport properties were investigated and compared in the presence of an activating additive. Results revealed an important difference in the oxide content of these materials, leading to a significantly better electronic power factor of Bi₂Te₃ synthesized through thermolysis route due to its lower extent of oxidation.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

All the chemicals used in the synthesis of Bi₂Te₃ were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Stockholm, Sweden) and were used as received, with no further purification: Bismuth chloride (BiCl₃, 98%), Tellurium powder (Te, 99.8%), sodium tellurite (Na₂TeO₃, 99%), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 97%), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (C₁₀H₁₆N₂O₈, EDTA, 98.5%), and sodium borohydride (NaBH₄, 98%), oleic acid (C₁₈H₃₄O₂), 1-Octadecene (C₁₈H₃₆, ODE), thioglycolic acid (C₂H₄O₂S, 98%, TGA), tri-butylphosphine (C₁₂H₂₇P, 93.5%, TBP). BiCl₃, and Te powder were precursors for Bi, and Te ions. Oleic acid, ODE, and TBP were used as solvents. TGA was used as a shape-directing agent. Methanol and Hexane (C₆H₁₄) were used to wash the as-synthesized particles.

The EPD media prepared with ethanol absolute (VWR, 99.8%), acetone (VWR, 99.5%), triethanolamine (TEA, Sigma-Aldrich, 99%) and acetonitrile (Thermo Fisher Scientific, LC-MS Grade). 1,6-Hexanedithiol (HS(CH₂)₆SH, HDT, Sigma Aldrich, 97%), was dissolved in 2-(1-Methoxy)propyl acetate (MPA, Acros Organics, 99%) and spin coated on the deposited films.

2.2. Synthesis of Bi₂Te₃ nanoparticles

Synthesis of Bi₂Te₃ was performed through hydrothermal and thermolysis routes, under MW-assisted heating (flexiWAVE–Milestone, 1800 Watt; multi-vessel high-pressure rotor). A schematic of the two processes is presented in Fig. 1. The hydrothermal synthesis and characterization of Bi₂Te₃ NPs was discussed in detail in our previous publication [27], therefore, here the process is reported briefly. In hydrothermal synthesis, bismuth (Bi) and tellurium (Te) precursors, (BiCl₃ and Na₂TeO₃) were mixed in a Teflon vial with a Bi:Te molar ratio of 2:3 in water. EDTA, and NaBH₄ were added to this mixture, and the pH was adjusted to the range of 10.5–11 by adding NaOH. The synthesis was performed in MW by heating to 220 °C within 4 min ramping and 2 min reaction time. Upon cooling, the particles were separated by centrifuging, followed by washing with isopropanol, acetone and water. After the washing step, the sample was dried in a vacuum oven overnight at 60 °C.

The sample is named Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ from hereon.

As for the synthesis of Bi₂Te₃ via thermolysis (or thermal decomposition), a stoichiometric amount of precursors was utilized to meet the Bi:Te molar ratio of 2:3. The Te powder was complexed with 6 mL of TBP by heating the mixture at 220 °C for 90 s using MW power of 400 W under constant stirring using MW synthesizer (Biotage® Initiator+) until all the Te powder was dissolved completely. In a separate vial Bi precursor solution was prepared by dissolving a stoichiometric amount of BiCl₃ in 16 mL of oleic acid under continuous stirring for 30 min, to ensure a homogeneous mixture. The solution was then transferred to a 100 mL Teflon vessel, followed by the addition of 8 mL ODE and 1 mL TGA. The final mixture was heated by MW to 220 °C with a ramp and dwell time of 4 min and 2 min, respectively. A black-colored product settling at the bottom of the vessel was obtained. The powder was separated from the solvent through centrifuging, followed by washing with acetone and isopropanol, followed by placing in a vacuum oven at 50 °C overnight for drying. The sample is named Thermo-Bi₂Te₃ from hereon.

2.3. Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) process

In the EPD process, the experimental setup consisted of a glass beaker containing the colloidal suspension, where particles are dispersed, and two electrodes placed inside the solution connected to a power source. The counter electrode was stainless steel, which is used to create an electric field between the two electrodes. The working electrode was also used as a substrate and it was made of soda lime glass with chromium (Cr) pattern on it. The details of the design and fabrication of the glass-based substrate via maskless photolithography (c/o Fig. S1) is presented in our previous publication [27]. Electrodes were connected to a power source (Votcraft CPPS-160-84) that is used in constant voltage mode to apply 80 V DC voltage. The distance between the electrodes was set to 1.5 cm.

EPD media for the deposition of Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ particles was prepared by dispersing 1 wt% particles in a 30 mL solution of ethanol (20 mL), acetone (10 mL), and 20 μL TEA. The suspension was ultrasonicated for 10 min in an ultrasonic bath (EMAG 12 HC) at maximum power at room temperature before the EPD. For the deposition of Thermo-Bi₂Te₃, 1.1 wt% particles dispersed in 25 mL acetonitrile solution was sonicated for 2 min with a probe sonicator (Sonics and Materials Inc) with 6 s pulses and 60% amplitude at room temperature. The deposition time was 3 min for Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ and 1.5 min for Thermo-Bi₂Te₃ particles to obtain EPD films with similar thickness.

A 100 μL solution of HDT and MPA, prepared with 1:1 ratio, was spin coated on the films to partially exchange the surface ligands and to improve the TE performance of the films. The films were then dried on a hot plate at 80 °C for 10 min. Prior to the evaluation of transport properties, a highly conductive silver (Ag) paste (Micro to Nano, 15-002142) was used to make electrical contacts. The contacts were partially placed on the TE film and partially on the glass substrate, and the measurements were done when the Ag contacts were fully dried. All

the processes are performed under ambient atmosphere.

2.4. Characterization of the as-synthesized particles

The crystalline phases were identified by using X-ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD). The PANalytical X'Pert PRO system, equipped with a Copper anode (Cu-K_{α1} radiation). The particle size and morphology analysis of the as-synthesized Bi₂Te₃ nanoparticles and EPD films was performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI Nova 200). Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) was used to obtain infrared spectra of as-made particles and EPD films in transmission mode (KBr Mini-Pellet Press, Specac; Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS10 FTIR spectrometer) in the range 4000–500 cm⁻¹.

2.5. Characterization of the EPD films

The evolution of the film microstructure was followed by SEM analysis (Fig. S2). The surface chemical composition of the EPD films has been investigated with X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). The non-monochromatized x-ray source with Mg anode lamp (Mg K_α line, 1253.6 eV) was used in all analysis. High-resolution photoelectron energy spectra were recorded with AES/XPS system EA10 (Leybold-Heraeus GmbH, Cologne, Germany) at room temperature. Pressure in the chamber during the measurements was less than 5 × 10⁻⁸ mbar. The spectrometer energy scale was calibrated using Au4f, Ag3d, and Cu2p lines, and furthermore all acquired spectra were calibrated to adventitious carbon C1s line at 285 eV. The overall resolution of the spectrometer during the measurements was estimated to be 0.96 eV, as the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the Ag3d5/2 line. The WSPeet version 8 (R. Unwin, 2001) data acquisition software was used to collect the data, and CasaXPS software version 2.3 (Casa Software Ltd., Teignmouth, UK) was used for data processing (deconvolution). To determine surface chemical composition, the wide range energy scan was collected, on the basis of which the detailed (high-resolution) scans of element emission lines were performed. The concentration of atoms in the sample was determined on the basis of XPS spectral analysis, considering the presence of individual elements.

Electronic transport properties of the EPD films were measured with the setup shown in Fig. 2, where the glass substrate with the deposited film is bridged between two Cu blocks with air gap in between. The Seebeck coefficient (*S*) was estimated through the integral method, in which one end of the film was heated with a Peltier module and the temperature of the other end held at room temperature. The TE voltage generated between the two ends of the EPD film was recorded continuously as a function of temperature, and the slope of the voltage vs temperature difference graph is used to estimate the *S* as $S = \Delta V / \Delta T$. Electrical resistance of the films was also measured as a function of temperature, and the electrical conductivity (σ) was estimated from the measured resistance values using the geometrical parameters of the films. The thickness of the EPD films were measured with Profiler KLA-Tencor P7. The electronic power factor ($PF = S^2 \sigma$) was calculated by

Fig. 1. Schematics of the synthesis process for Bi₂Te₃ nanoparticles through MW-assisted hydrothermal and thermolysis routes.

Fig. 2. Sketch (not drawn to scale) showing the transport measurement set-up. The EPD film shown in light gray, was deposited on the glass-based substrate (shown in light blue color) with Cr lines on it. The line width and separation distance between the Cr lines were $10\ \mu\text{m}$ and transport measurements done perpendicular to these lines, by placing the probes onto the Ag contacts.

using the measured S and calculated σ of the samples using the resistance and geometrical parameters. The EPD films had a length of $\sim 1\ \text{cm}$, width of $\sim 0.5\ \text{cm}$, and a thickness of $\sim 30\ \mu\text{m}$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of as-synthesized particles

MW-assisted synthesis enabled the preparation of TE nanostructures in a time and energy-efficient manner (7 min including ramping time), with a reaction yield of 98%. Crystal structure and phase purity of the as-synthesized materials are evaluated using XRPD. The diffraction patterns are presented in Fig. 3. The crystalline phases are indexed to Bi_2Te_3 (ICDD: 01-085-0439) with rhombohedral crystal structure, and indexing of the diffraction peaks with the corresponding Miller indices are shown on the diffraction patterns.

Morphology of the as-synthesized Bi_2Te_3 are studied using SEM, and few micrographs are presented in Fig. 4. Micrographs shown in Fig. 4(a)-(b) are for the Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 sample, while Fig. 4(c)-(d) are for the Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 sample. Platelet morphology was observed in both samples. The average lateral size of the platelets is estimated from the SEM micrographs as $177 \pm 68\ \text{nm}$ for the Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 and $66 \pm 16\ \text{nm}$ for Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 sample. The thickness of the platelets also shows some differences, where Hydro-NPs exhibit (thicknesses in the range of 8–28 nm) an average value of $14 \pm 4\ \text{nm}$, and the Thermo-sample shows an average value of $36 \pm 11\ \text{nm}$ (thicknesses in the range of 20–60 nm). The observed platelet morphology is controlled by the use of structure directing agents as EDTA in the synthesis of Hydro- Bi_2Te_3

and TGA in the synthesis of Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 . These additives adsorb and stabilize the Bi_2Te_3 nanocrystals in the c-plane, enforcing their growth in the lateral direction, leading to the formation of the observed anisotropic nanostructures.

3.2. Electronic transport properties of EPD films

Transport properties of the films prepared through the EPD of Thermo- and Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 NPs are presented in Fig. 5 as a function of the hot side temperature (T_h), or the temperature difference between the hot and cold ends, ΔT . All the measurements were performed under ambient atmosphere. Although the EPD films are fabricated through electromigration of the suspended particles leading to strongly percolating particle network, resistance measurements.

on the as-made films show open circuit behavior. Measurable resistance values are reached only after the treatment with HDT via spin coating. The positive effect of thiol molecules on the electronic transport has been discussed in earlier works [27–30]. Upon creation of a temperature gradient, the film develops a negative voltage, indicating the n-type character of the transport through the deposited material - as expected from stoichiometric Bi_2Te_3 . The thermovoltage linearly increases in absolute value with increasing ΔT , as shown in Fig. 5a within the measured temperature range. Using this data the Seebeck coefficients (S) are estimated and are presented in Fig. 5b; the Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 sample shows an initial S value of $-159\ \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ at $T_h\ 295\ \text{K}$ ($\approx 22\ ^\circ\text{C}$), increasing gradually and stabilizing at $-153\ \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ at $325\ \text{K}$ ($\approx 52\ ^\circ\text{C}$), while the Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 sample starts at $-166\ \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$, after a small reduction shows a steady value reaching $-179\ \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ at $323\ \text{K}$.

Slightly higher $|S|$ value of Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 sample will be discussed in Section 3.4, after the detailed surface analysis below.

Resistance measurements on Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 yielded a value of $1.65\ \text{k}\Omega$, slightly decreasing to $1.55\ \text{k}\Omega$ at the highest T (see Fig. 5c), while Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 NPs [27] exhibited an initial resistance of $13\ \text{k}\Omega$, linearly reducing to $11.7\ \text{k}\Omega$ at $323\ \text{K}$ on the hot side (Fig. 5). A more reasonable comparison would be on the basis of conductivity (σ), as it considers the geometrical parameters of the films. The σ as a function of the T_h is presented in Fig. 5d, where room temperature values are obtained as $0.017\ \text{S}/\text{cm}$ and $0.131\ \text{S}/\text{cm}$, respectively. The values for the Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 sample are about 8 times lower than that of Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 . This difference can be due to several factors such as surface roughness, presence of oxide layers (as scatterers of charge carriers, or energy barriers), and localized imperfections at the interface. Looking closer to their microstructure, one can see smaller and irregular shaped particles in the case of Hydro-synthesis, while larger particles with platelet morphology are obtained in the case of Thermo-sample. Particles' surface chemistry are significantly influenced by the synthetic

Fig. 3. X-ray powder diffraction patterns of Bi_2Te_3 nanoparticles synthesised via MW-assisted hydrothermal and thermolysis routes. The major crystalline phases are indexed to Bi_2Te_3 (ICDD: 01-085-0439), with rhombohedral crystal structure.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of Bi_2Te_3 nanoparticles synthesized through Thermo- (a and b) and Hydro- (c and d) routes, at different magnifications.

process; i.e. the solvent, precursors and additives used. A more detailed discussion on the transport properties is presented in Section 3.4, subsequent to the XPS analysis below.

3.3. XPS analysis of EPD films

EDX analysis (spectra presented in Fig. S3) on the EPD films treated with HDT clearly reveal the presence of sulfur. In order to evaluate the role of sulfur we performed FT-IR analysis on the as-made particles, HDT and EPD films after HDT treatment. A representative FT-IR spectrum of HDT treated EPD film is given in Fig. S4. As there is no sulfur specific signal observed in the FT-IR spectrum, the data is inconclusive needing further analysis with surface sensitive techniques. Thereafter, XPS analysis was performed on the EPD films of Bi_2Te_3 NPs after the treatment with HDT; the resultant spectra for C1s, Bi4f-S2p, Te3d, and O1s regions are presented in Fig. 6. Carbon residue is present on both the samples, reaching 61.3% in Hydro-sample, and a higher content of 67.76% for the Thermo-sample. In case of oxygen, the situation is similar. A summary of XPS peak fitting results is presented in Table 1. Metallic and oxide phases of Bi and Te were identified with the deconvolution process, clearly visible in Te3d and Bi4f regions for both the samples. It is a well-known problem with overlap of S2p with Bi4f signal in XPS; the procedure applied for their deconvolution is explained in details in the supplementary materials (c/o Section 3 and Fig. S5). A comparison of percentage of metal oxides for Bi and Te with respect to the total elemental concentration shows a significantly higher level of metal (Te) oxide content for Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 sample. This is a major difference that may have contributed to the consistently lower σ values observed in Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 film as compared to the Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 film.

A strong signal of sulfur (S) has been observed in both the films, as they have been treated with HDT, where Thermo- Bi_2Te_3 film showed about 3.5% higher percentage of sulfur when compared to Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 . The binding energy of 163.5 eV identified for sulfur is generally ascribed to covalently bonded S(0)-sulfide, or thiol groups (C-S-H). This also confirms that thiols are part of the EPD films, making a significant impact on the interfacial resistance in both the cases as discussed in the transport section.

3.4. Impact of surface chemistry and porosity on the electronic transport

Based on the XPS data one may model the system as a composite material, using the effective medium theory, as the grains of Bi_2Te_3 with metal oxide (Bi and Te oxide) coating as the grain boundaries. The model assumes that the composite material consists of a mixture of the two phases and that their contributions to the S can be combined based on their volume fractions (ϕ) by using the following equation: $S_{\text{eff}} = \phi \cdot S_{\text{grain}} + (1 - \phi) \cdot S_{\text{gb}}$. In our earlier work [29], we have studied percolation behavior of hybrid TE materials, where we observed a steady value for S , while the resistance showed significant dependence on the percolating network. Therefore, the effective medium theory can be applied to provide an estimate of grain (S_{grain}) and grain boundary (S_{gb}) contributions to the S_{eff} . We have previously evaluated the S of sintered Hydro- Bi_2Te_3 nanopowder, which can be approximated as the bulk, or grain value (S_{grain}). Using the S value of $-140 \mu\text{V/K}$ at room temperature [10], we see higher magnitude of $|S|$ for both the samples, where the boundaries are composed of non-conducting oxide phases with significantly higher S values; the S for Bi_2O_3 is reported as $550 \mu\text{V/K}$ [32] while that of TeO_2 as $522 \mu\text{V/K}$ [33]. By employing the

Fig. 5. Transport properties of EPD film of Bi₂Te₃ NPs synthesised through Hydro (at 80 V, 3 min) and Thermo (at 80 V, 1.5 min) routes: (a) Output voltage (ΔV) as a function of temperature difference (ΔT), (b) Seebeck coefficient, S calculated from (a), versus hot side temperature (T_h), (c) resistance, and (d) electrical conductivity, σ versus T_h (T_c is kept at 22 °C, 295 K).

equation above, S_{eff} of the composite material can be calculated as a weighted average of S of the individual phases. Taking an average value of S for surface oxides as 530 $\mu V/K$ one would obtain a higher magnitude of S_{eff} for the Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ sample due to its higher oxide, or grain boundary, content as experimentally measured. The ϕ_{gb} (i.e. $1 - \phi$) estimated from this fitting is 0.7% for Hydro- and 0.3% for Thermo-Bi₂Te₃, which are in line with the observed oxide content in the two films. These values are useful to provide insight for the drastically different σ values.

These results can not be directly compared with the transport properties obtained on conventionally sintered pellet samples, where all the organic capping agents are removed prior to sintering at elevated temperature in oxygen-free atmosphere. Otherwise, their presence during sintering creates carbonaceous residues at the grain boundaries, influencing the charge transport. There is a report on the size dependent transport properties, where the authors have studied the synthesis of Bi₂Te₃ nanoparticles with various sizes, using capping agents with different hydrocarbon chain length and at different reaction temperatures [13]. The resultant electronic transport properties of the surface capped samples, measured after compaction into pellets (packing density of about 87%), showed two orders of magnitude decrease in σ from 1×10^{-3} S/cm for 17 nm particles to 5.8×10^{-5} S/cm for 29 nm particles, while the S values for the samples (synthesized at 50 °C) remain the same at -49 $\mu V/K$ showing no clear size dependence. Our conductivity values are one to two order of magnitude higher than these samples, despite a higher porosity in our films, while our S values are ≥ 3 times higher than these samples.

The presented as-made porous EPD films are made of nanoparticles and molecular junctions, without the use of high temperature-pressure processing. It is known that the porosity adversely affects the electronic transport properties. The higher the porosity, the larger is the interfacial area between the TE material and voids, along with the

oxidized interface at the nanoscale. Those changes disturb the free carriers by trapping and scattering them more severely as the porosity is increased. In order to give a perspective, we may compare the trends with findings on porous TEs. There is a recent report focusing on porous TEs based on Sb_{1.5}Bi_{0.5}Te₃ (SBT), where a slurry was directly printed and sintered (at 500–550 °C) to burn out all the organics. The reported σ value is two orders of magnitude lower than the values obtained for materials through conventional methods, due to the porous nature of the sintered material [34]. A similar trend has been reported on polysilicon, where the effect of systematically increased porosity has been investigated. The σ was shown to decrease about ten to thousand times for porosity levels of 62% and 80%, respectively [35].

The activation energy (E_a) of conduction in EPD films was estimated from Arrhenius plots ($\ln \sigma$ vs $1000/T$, presented in Fig. S6) as 0.019 eV and 0.034 eV for Thermo- and Hydro-Bi₂Te₃, respectively. The higher E_a for the Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ sample can be attributed to the higher surface oxide percent at the interfaces, that is certainly originating from the synthetic route, as water as the solvent facilitates the oxide formation. The electrical power factor (PF) is calculated using the S and σ values, as presented in Fig. S7, reaching to values in the order of 0.18–0.24 $\mu W/m.K^2$ for the Thermo-Bi₂Te₃ sample, and 0.05–0.06 $\mu W/m.K^2$ for the Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ sample. The difference mainly originates from their significantly different σ values in connection to their surface chemistry inherited from the synthetic process. Porosity and surface chemistry (oxide content) dominate the σ , leading naturally to low power factor values when compared to conventional energetically-processed materials.

Several features of the developed methodology, including room temperature and solution processability, no need for inert atmosphere, or high temperature-pressure treatment (i.e. sintering or annealing), long term chemical stability of the films' performance over time, scalability of the process and its low cost can make these films promising for

Fig. 6. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) survey scan, and C1s, Bi4f-S2p, and Te3d spectra for EPD films of HDT treated Thermo- and Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ nanoparticles.

next generation TE generators or coatings, where the selection of the synthetic methodology for TE materials should ideally be based on thermolysis.

The developed porous TE platform enables the study of interfacial processes, in relation to the synthetic process and the resultant surface chemistry, in the electronic transport based on the nanoparticle characteristics (morphology, size, surface chemistry) and type of additives used. Further work is required to identify and study the mechanisms to improve the performance of the EPD films, by the use of solid/liquid electrolytes, or conducting polymers in the porous matrix.

4. Conclusion

Bi₂Te₃ particles with high phase purity was synthesized using thermolysis and hydrothermal routes in a matter of minutes, owing to the use of MW-assisted heating. EPD films were deposited with 80 V applied voltage and ≤ 3 min deposition time. Transport properties, including the Seebeck coefficient and electrical resistance were measured in a temperature gradient. The films showed electronic activity only after treatment with HDT, and they displayed comparable Seebeck values, while the conductivity of the Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ sample is about 8 times lower than the Thermo-Bi₂Te₃ sample. Both the films show the presence of sulfur on their surface, upon to the treatment with HDT, attributed to

its linkage to nanoparticles' surface through sulfide formation. A closer analysis of surface chemistry showed some differences, revealing a higher level of metal oxides in the Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ EPD film. The activation energy of conduction is estimated using Arrhenius equation for the EPD films, revealing a significantly higher E_a value in the Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ sample (0.034 eV for Hydro-Bi₂Te₃ vs. 0.019 eV for Thermo-Bi₂Te₃), mainly attributed to the presence of higher surface oxide content. These results clearly indicate the effect of the synthetic methods used on the nanoparticle surface chemistry, which in turn impacted the resultant transport properties revealing a better transport property for the materials synthesized through thermolysis. This work provides a viable route and platform for a detailed study of surface-interface related transport characteristics, for a conscious choice of the synthetic strategy for an effective material design. Based on our findings, we recommend the use of thermolysis route for the further development of nanoparticle-based TE films and modules for waste-heat harvesting anywhere that a ΔT can be exploited.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hamawandi Bejan: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Szukiewicz Rafal:** Formal analysis. **Björn Ergül Adem:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology,

Table 1

XPS peak fitting results for C1s, Bi4f, Te3d, S2p and O1s regions for EPD films of Hydro- and Thermo-Bi₂Te₃ after treatment with HDT.

Samples	BE [eV] [31]	Fraction	Assigned to
Thermo-Bi ₂ Te ₃	285	67.76	C C-C, C-O, O-C=O
	157	0.71	Bi Bi: 0.18 (25.52% total Bi)
	159		Bi-O (Bi ₂ O ₃): 0.53 (74.49% total Bi)
	573	1.73	Te Te: 0.87 (50.44% total Te)
	577		Te-O (TeO ₂): 0.86 (49.56% total Te)
Hydro-Bi ₂ Te ₃	532	9.26	O Oxide (34.36%), O-C=O (60.52%), OH - groups (5.12%)
	163.5	14.75	S S(0) (C-S-C), sulfide, or -SH
	285	61.28	C C-O, C-C, O-C=O
	157	4.81	Bi Bi: 1.41 (29.33% total Bi)
	159		Bi-O (Bi ₂ O ₃): 3.4 (70.67% total Bi)
	573	6.85	Te Te: 2.06 (30% total Te)
	577		Te-O (TeO ₂): 4.80 (70% total Te)
532	13.85	O Oxide (55.06%), O-C=O (38.63%), OH - groups (6.31%)	
163.5	11.22	S S(0) (C-S-C), sulfide, or -SH	

Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Toprak Muhammet S:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Kuchowicz Maciej:** Formal analysis. **Batili Hazal:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2023.132898](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2023.132898).

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